

A New NTN Paradigm: **HAPS / HIBS**

10.5281/zenodo.13994427

Halim Yanikomeroglu
Chancellor's Professor
Non-Terrestrial Networks Lab
Systems and Computer Engineering
Carleton University

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6G+

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all integrated

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all integrated

more than LEOs

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6G+

all integrated

more than LEOs

more than connectivity

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A New NTN Paradigm: HAPS / HIBS

6G+

all integrated

more than LEOs

more than connectivity

more than rural & remote

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Agenda

- Introductory Remarks
- HAPS (High Altitude Platform Station) / HIBS Networks
- Research Directions
- Concluding Remarks

ITU-R WP5D
"IMT 2030 and beyond" (6G) vision
22 June 2023

Capabilities of IMT-2030

NOTE: The range of values given for capabilities are estimated targets for research and investigation of IMT-2030.

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Big opportunities for **NTN** in the next three decades

HAPS: High Altitude Platform Station → HIBS

HAPS: “A station on an object at an altitude of 20 to 50 km and at a specified, nominal, **fixed point relative to the Earth**” (ITU Radio Regulations, Article 1.66A).

HIBS: HAPS as an IMT (International Mobile Telecommunications) Base Station
HIBS altitude: 18-25 km (WRC-23)

WWRF50 – NTN Panel

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SPL (UK)
hydrogen fuel
20 kW power to the antenna
3m diameter antenna
480 individually steerable beams
Up to 140 km diameter coverage
equivalent to 450 masts
up to 200 Mbps

No. 5, 2019

Managing spectrum for evolving technologies

Special Edition
World Radiocommunication Conference 2019

Strong interest in ITU since 1990s for **rural and remote coverage**

HAPS **dedicated (non-IMT) spectrum** allocations: WRC 1997, ..., WRC 2019

“The studies (see Report ITU–R F.2438-0 (11/2018)) indicate that there is a need for almost 3 GHz of additional spectrum for HAPS to meet the requirements of certain applications.”

“This is much more than the 600 MHz that are currently identified worldwide for HAPS operating in the fixed service (additionally, to the fixed service identifications, some bands were identified for HAPS operating in the mobile service as IMT base stations).”

2030 (5G/6G) scenario:
IMT spectrum
rural & remote areas

ITU Publications

International Telecommunication Union
Radiocommunication Sector

World Radiocommunication Conference 2023 (WRC-23)

Provisional Final Acts

Establishment WRC-23 Agenda Item 1.4 Aiming at expansion of the frequency bands for HIBS

Current Regulation

NO FLEXIBILITY

Candidate bands for WRC-23

FLEXIBILITY

“HAPS industry’s expectation of this agenda item

- Allow to use of more frequency bands that are currently prohibited for HIBS by the RR.
- These frequency ranges (694-960 MHz, 1.7-2.1 GHz and 2.6 GHz) have been assigned to almost all MNOs around world, that enables MNOs to use HIBS with flexible frequency selection.”

Source: WRC-23 Report, SoftBank, 19 Dec 2023

VHetNet: Terrestrial BSs + HAPS BSs in Urban Areas

- ◆ Owned/shared by the legacy operators, part of the 3GPP ecosystem
- ◆ Vertical HetNet (VHetNet): One single network with multiple tiers
super macro BS (SMBS) ← macro BS ← small BS
10-100 km ← few km ← 100 m

SMBS: native

M. Alzenad, H. Yanikomeroglu, “Coverage and rate analysis for vertical heterogeneous networks (VHetNets)”, *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, Dec 2019.

N. Cherif, M. Alzenad, H. Yanikomeroglu, A. Yongacoglu, “Downlink coverage and rate analysis of an aerial user in vertical heterogeneous networks (VHetNets)”, *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, Mar 2021.

G. Kurt, M.G. Khoshkholgh, S. Alfattani, A. Ibrahim, T.S.J. Darwish, Md S. Alam, H. Yanikomeroglu, A. Yongacoglu, “A vision and framework for the high altitude platform station (HAPS) networks of the future”, *IEEE Communications Surveys and Tutorials*, Q2 2021.

S. Alam, G. Karabulut Kurt, H. Yanikomeroglu, N.D. Dao, P. Zhu, “High altitude platform station based super macro base station (HAPS-SMBS) constellations”, *IEEE Communications Magazine*, Jan 2021.

HAPS: High Altitude Platform Station

HAPS: Super Macro Base Station in Stratosphere (20 km)

G. Kurt, M.G. Khoshkholgh, S. Alfattani, A. Ibrahim, T.S.J. Darwish, Md S. Alam, H. Yanikomeroglu, A. Yongacoglu, “A vision and framework for the high altitude platform station (HAPS) networks of the future”, *IEEE Communications Surveys and Tutorials*, Q2 2021.

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HAPS: High Altitude Platform Station

LTE specifies four preamble formats to accommodate longer round trip propagation delays in large cells.
PRACH preamble format 1: up to 48 miles
PRACH preamble format 3: up to 62 miles

HAPS: Super Macro Base Station in Stratosphere (20 km)

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HAPS: High Altitude Platform Station - Urban/Suburban Regions

HAPS: Super Macro Base Station in Stratosphere (20 km)

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No. 5, 2019

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beyond 2030 (6G/B6G) scenario:
urban/suburban (metro) areas

Integrated with terrestrial network
in harmonized spectrum

- One air-interface
- One device
- One network

...ational spectrum for HAPS to meet the requirements of certain applications."

"This is much more than the 600 MHz that are currently identified worldwide for HAPS operating in the fixed service (additionally, to the fixed service identifications, some bands were identified for HAPS operating in the mobile service as IMT base stations)."

VHetNet: Terrestrial BSs + HAPS BSs in Urban/Suburban Areas

VHetNet: Terrestrial BSs + HAPS BSs in Urban/Suburban Areas

Ubiquitous & Instantaneous Hotspot – Anytime, Anywhere, Affordable

20 km

HAPS: High Altitude Platform Station

Ubiquitous & Instantaneous Hotspot – Anytime, Anywhere, Affordable

20 km

HAPS: High Altitude Platform Station

centralized massive
access capacity
provided through
dynamic beams
wherever necessary,
whenever necessary

0.2° beamwidth @ 20 km
→ 70 m diameter hotspot

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HAPS-enabled Wireless Infrastructure towards 2050

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HAPS-enabled Wireless Infrastructure towards 2050

Distributed massive antenna architecture

Distributed edge and data centre

5G/6G/7G air-interface

RF/FSO for backhaul

- IoT: 100 km diameter
- Hotspot: 70 m diameter (0.2° beamwidth)

HAPS-enabled Wireless Infrastructure towards 2050

Integrated terrestrial – HAPS
– LEO network: VHetNet

Access + backhaul + edge
+ transport + core + spectrum
+ optical → infrastructure

Integrated communications,
computing, sensing,
navigation, positioning, ...

10,000 – 100,000+ HAPS

Transformative

- IoT: 100 km diameter
- Hotspot: 70 m diameter (0.2° beamwidth)

Distributed massive antenna architecture

Distributed edge and data centre

5G/6G/7G air-interface

RF/FSO for backhaul

HAPS Networks Research @ Carleton (ICT)

- 1) Access
- 2) Backhaul | Transport
- 3) Integration | Interference Management
- 4) Antenna Architectures
- 5) Edge Intelligence
- 6) Spectrum | Propagation
- 7) Sensing
- 8) Navigation | Localization | Positioning
- 9) Control | Management
- 10) Cybersecurity
- 11) Sustainability | Greenness
- 12) Advanced PHY for high spectral efficiency
- 13) Emerging Technologies (RIS, digital twins, quantum key distribution, ...)

non-ICT

- 1) Aircraft endurance
- 2) Loitering time
- 3) Energy
- 4) Material science
- 5) Policy/Regulations

Interference Management +

HAPS-Only Network Serving Terrestrial Users
Legacy (before WRC-23) ITU scenario

Interference Management ++

Integrated HAPS-Terrestrial Macro Base Stations
No overlapping coverage region (WRC-23 scenario)

WRC-23 operation (Agenda item 1.4)
No-Interference, No-Protection (**NINP**):
The operation of this device/system must not cause interference to other licensed radio apparatus and will not normally be protected from interference, including interference that may cause undesired operation of the device/system.

Interference Management +++

Fully Integrated HAPS-Terrestrial Macro Base Stations and Small Cells HAPS in urban/suburban areas (2030s onward)

Anticipated WRC-27 & WRC-31 scenarios

A. Yadav, H. Yanikomeroglu, "Cell-edge capacity improvement via FD-HAPS", u/r in *IEEE Trans Communications*, 2024.

I. Cumali, B. Ozbek, G. Karabulut Kurt, H. Yanikomeroglu, "User selection and codebook design for NOMA-based high altitude platform station (HAPS) communications", *IEEE Trans. Vehicular Technology*, Mar 2023.

M. Salamatmoghadasi, A. Mehrabian, H. Yanikomeroglu, "Energy sustainability in dense radio access networks via high altitude platform stations", *IEEE Wireless Networking Letters (Early Access)*, 2023.

B. Ciloglu, G. Berkay Koc, M. Ozturk, H. Yanikomeroglu, "Cell switching in HAPS-aided networking: How the obscurity of traffic loads affects the decision", u/r in *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, 2023.

A. Alidadi Shamsabadi, A. Yadav, H. Yanikomeroglu, "Enhancing next-generation urban connectivity: Is integrated HAPS-terrestrial network a solution?", u/r in *IEEE Commun Letters*, 2023.

A. Alidadi Shamsabadi, A. Yadav, O. Abbasi, H. Yanikomeroglu, "Handling interference in integrated HAPS-terrestrial networks through radio resource management", *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, Dec 2022.

Advanced Antenna Systems: Cambridge Consultants + SPL (Deutsche Telekom)

Started in late 2010s

Antenna: 3 m², 120 kg

480 individually steerable beams

powered by 4096 radios

Total capacity > 100 Gbps

Target: 2024+

Advanced Antenna Systems: SoftBank

O. Abbasi, H. Yanikomeroglu, G. Kaddoum, "Hemispherical antenna array architecture for high-altitude platform stations (HAPS) for uniform capacity provision", u/r in *IEEE Transactions Wireless Communications*, 2023.

R. Shafie, M.J. Omid, O. Abbasi, H. Yanikomeroglu, "MIMO-NOMA enabled sectorized cylindrical massive antenna array for HAPS with spatially correlated channels", u/r in *IEEE Transactions Wireless Communications*, 2023.

Concluding Remarks

HAPS / HIBS:

A new network infrastructure layer in stratosphere
(between the terrestrial and space layers)

Non a single technology,
a colossal infrastructure paradigm with unprecedented opportunities

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Why not?

YouTube: Halim Yanikomeroglu
halim@sce.carleton.ca

Linear **HAPS** Constellation for Neom City

